
Legal Reforms in Anti-Terrorism Act 1997 in Pakistan

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ABSTRACT: The definition of terrorism in this Act is without adequate protection against the abuse and misuse of terrorism law. This law is also inadequate to achieve the purpose, i.e. to punish and counter the terrorism. Last decade in Pakistan, there is a loophole in present law to combat and punish the terrorist. However, this loophole is also due to political will of successive government that is not achieving terrorism law's goal. Due to this reason, anti-terrorism law was selectively used not equally based use. The offence of kidnapping and abduction may be omitted in this clause 4 (i) Third Schedule because it can be appropriately mixed within present provisions of the ATA. Terrorist offences investigation, including interceptor or surveillance should be handled under the scheme of IFTA's because such offences come under 2013 IFTA preview.

Keywords: Protection, Loophole, Kidnaping, Abduction, IFTA, Schedule

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1. Introduction

Terrorism has no boundary or religion. Not only Pakistan but also whole world is engulfed by the terrorism. It is in the form of a national movement for liberty, political struggle, sectarian conflict, cross border ethnicity issue etc. It affect poor and weak nation. Its aim is to slow peace development. There are cross claims in our territory. Regardless, the presence of the anti-terrorism system, terrorism and extremists has grown alarming level in Pakistan. There is a need to change Pakistan Anti-Terrorism Laws. This changing should be taking place from the start definition section6. To study of Section 6 ATA 1997, it is clear that in this section consist of legislative defect that is spread unwarranted level. But there are some recommendation discussed in this thesis work that in Pakistan this Act could not cover criminal law, because the presence of terrorism law cover all areas which aren't present in ordinary criminal law.

There are also a large number of differences in present ATA 1997 court management and power, so it is easy to change such area. It is mentioned above that there are a large number of discrepancies present in the work of ATCs. In the interpretation of law by judges that all party persons are present and take speedy proceeding. There are also no evidentiary criteria to declare an organization proscribe. To shield the right of

individual and organization, there should be specific criteria to declare proscribing an organization or individual. There should be given right of review to proscribe organized by review committee.

2. Recommendations Section 6 Definitions

In order to clear requirement of intention, the wording of threat use should be amended threat is made with or use intention. Additionally, there should be explanatory in the section that underlines the involvement of people in terrorism offence as an integral element.

The words “create insecurity or in point of fright in society would be excluded to the ambit of ATA application. The point of insecurity, fear is a broad implication than intimidation, coercion and subduing. This section parlance is uncertain and unclear to perform it efficiently. In other jurisdictions, the menacing word is applied in many ways to the elimination of ‘insecurity and fright’ sufficiently to capture terrorism in the society.

The intention of the legislation behind under defined should be clear and explanatory notes that point out terrorism from other serious crimes i.e. robbery, assault, murder or rape. The violence done by public or political reasons is different to the violence by private i.e. jealousy, greed, revenge etc. This sub-clause should also be removed from Anti-Terrorism (Second Amendment) Act 2013 as discussed above reasons. By the introduction of additional reasons i.e. “religion, ethnic or sectarian under this sub-section formed multifaceted terrorism in Pakistan”. To the insertion of racial, political or ideological caused has stopped the politically motivated violence such as in Karachi.

The extent of section 6(3) is reduced to the extent of sub-section 2 that include the use of explosive and not involve firearm action or another arm instrument. Therefore, it is not easy to know the work of explosive material, is not planning to coerce or intimidate the public or government for reason of advancing religion, sectarian or ethnic cause etc. In the presence of this provision, remain suspicious. The explosive use and no action involve by firearm or weapon is mentioned under sub-section (2). But it is a difficult situation that use of explosive isn't planned to coerce or intimidate the general public or this explosive substance use for advancing an ethnic, religious or sectarian or other cause. Therefore, in the presence of this provision creates doubt and omission of this provision may be considered.

The sub-section 6 (2)(c) should be omitted in the 2013 Amendment because it is not serving any purpose for the effectiveness of the provision. If the ambient of this section is reduced by legislation, then it only covers the attack on schools, hospitals, government premises, and office installation. Therefore, it needs to design this sub-section more restricted manner and eliminate the property private or public. Additionally, this sub-section exclude any damage of property, arson looting. The severe destruction of property words should be exchanged by serious damage or harm of property.

Recommendations Communication System

The extent of this sub-section should be expanded and it needs to eliminate particular references to public utility service or communication system and exchange with wide reference to an essential infrastructure facility or an electronic system. Alternative reliance may be exchanged with censorious building, i.e. substance benefit, service or system if damaged, disrupted, damaged by cyber or physical signifies that will endanger public health, national security risk, and public confidence becomes lower, economic security threatens or brings the national disgrace.

Recommendations Explosive substance

The section 6 (2)(ee) of the 2013 Amendment should be omitted because having explosive substance without lawful reason caused strict liability offence and no need of mensrea. Therefore, it should be separately made an offence under the ATA and not need to accompany other section. The words bomb blast should replace with the use of an explosives device.

The provoking of ethnic, religious or sectarian hatred should be removed in this section and it constitutes a different crime and it has own criteria in this act. Recommendations Fundamental rights

This research finds that there are many legislative defects in this sub-section 6 (2)(p). The wording of this provision is unusually wide, which creates a violation of the fundamental right under constitution, i.e. freedom of religion, freedom of speech. Another interesting point in this sub-section FM stations is not illegal. It means that everyone discusses his idea and belief on the radio without permission of government if such discussion is regarded with the terrorist. It cannot be contradicted that government rule about the circulation of religious ideas, teaching and beliefs. If these ideas are opposite in Pakistan rule, then such activities come under terrorism and these are regulated in ATA.

However, if these activities are included in this Act then it may be adjusted outside of the provision of section 6 associates with hatred speech. In such a situation much care needs to legislate in drafting that steps are adequate and are not derogate fundamental rights under the constitution.

Recommendations Offence of Kidnapping etc

The offence of kidnapping and abduction may be omitted in this clause 4 (i) Third Schedule because it can be appropriately mixed within present provisions of the ATA. Commission of kidnapping with intimidation or coercion of government or public for the purpose of caring sectarian, religious or ethnic reasons that may constitute terrorism can already be adjusted under section 6. Particular reference may be made for kidnapping or abduction carries out for fund raising for terrorism by terrorist organizations in section 11 (H) of this act. If there is such offence has taken place for terrorism or its organization, so it constitutes a separate offence and sentence implement under this Act.

The use of or firearms already and attack on the worship place falls within the ambit of subsection 6 (2)(ee) and (2)(h). Likewise, the use of explosives or firearms in the premises of the court would be discussed under Section 6(2).

If legislation has the intention to add such offence and make strict accountability, the use of word 'fireman and explosives by a device, i.e. bomb blast' should be deleted because it is creating uncertainty.

Recommendations fire upon

In section 5(2)(i) 'when fired upon' word should be omitted. The restriction to the prevention of terrorism on armed forces, police and civil forces should be changed by section 96-106 of PPC and dealing with 'Right to Private Defense'. These are followed:

- a) When there is fear of death or grievous hurt towards individual so right of force should be used. This reasonable fear of attack may be by the police or public.
- b) In the last step for defense is forced to die.
- c) The use of force has to equal the apprehension of an attack.
- d) Force use is to prevent threat or attack.
- e) The final step is court as arbitrator.

Recommendations Create Special Investigator

A particular group of terrorism investigator should be created in the provinces. Because ATA is not good for restructuring the police, but it helps for re drafting of ATA and make place for the commission for the terrorism investigation. All the member of investigator team submits report with Challah to the ATC judge and Prosecutor. There must be meeting between member, operation command, police, intelligence agencies, etc. for the cooperation and sharing the report with JITs. This all process should be conducted under terrorism authority. The task Forces being made to attack and down the terrorist group or organization. In this regard, the aim of forces is to stop terrorism.

Recommendations Investigation

Terrorist offences investigation, including interceptor or surveillance should be handled under the scheme of IFTA's because such offences come under 2013 IFTA preview. If the situation is not allowed to consume the procedure and warrant obtain under IFTA by the high court, then ATA give a special method for emergency. This emergency mechanism warrants for the interception or surveillance is given to an investigator or JIT to request the High Court Judge. But the limitation period of the warrant should be specific time than IFTA warrants. For confidential information needs a strong method that it will not disclose to the public or unauthorized person.

To introduce modern method of investigation i.e. plea-bargain, relative guilt and polygraph testing. There should be effective forensic support in terrorism cases.

Recommendations Cordon Police Circle

The designation of cordon (police circle) should be extended only operation areas. It will give the lawful shield in more sensitive areas of the city. To designate Special Area Operation should be given by civil armed forces or armed forces and addition to the police are placed under section 4 of the ATA.

The selection of special areas of operation has two categories. First, it would allow all power, i.e. police, civil armed forces and armed forces under section 21 –B. In category to it, take measures to stop entry and exit have selected operation area and apply the curfew there. The Provincial Home Secretary authorized this category. Under section, 21-E of this Act duration for remand should be reduced and the remanded duration is not equal to the preventive detention under this Act. More than 30 days remand must be extended by strong based of the evidence. Medical official examine remanded the person if he is in custody of other person than the police. In presence of any torture proof the other person loss legal to grasp the accused than police has responsibility of his custody.

Recommendations Disposal of Property

The disposal of property it is needed to police officer has approach adequate authority to order. ATC's must be decided appropriate authority. Order of prohibition by the police property disposal must be made succeeding 10 days. It is the duty to give sanction for opening information. In case it is approved, then the punishment will be 2 years imprisonment, fine, or both. This punishment is equally awarded in case of not complying with police in order to supply the information under section 21-EE.

Recommendation Proscribe Organization

The criteria of this section need to add direct language of the ATA to improve proscription standard or stand single but Federal Government issued guidelines. Additionally, for the guideline of proscription there may be new schedule added to the end of justice and transparency.

It is suggested that proscribe organizations Review Committee rule clearly mentioned and also the procedure to examine the application in this section. It is also necessary that Federal Government explain the process to initiate the committee. There should be also necessary to mention the Review Committee officials are above particular grade from other governmental departments.

It is suggested that the right of appeal should be granted to proscribe organizations for the purpose to carry their charitable activities. There should impose duty on proscribe organization to open the things, names list of all official, their organization structure and scales. It is also disclosing the funding of the organization, the office addresses and other organization names, which gives support. For financial clarity, it should also disclose information of financial support. The law enforcement agencies also inspect the building which the organizations are use of charitable purposes. If it is reasonable to believe that office or building has used by organization for terrorist activities. So following inspection power use

- a) To check the profession or business activates of charge organization person.
- b) To inspect all found record and information of that said premises.
- c) To give information about these records or other by the premise of the any person.
- d) To inspect the source of cash that found in the building and to ask questions about the source of it.

Additionally, there should also situation for disclosing that he is not involved in terrorist activity and to run the revocation organization for charitable work.

Recommendations Punishment Terrorist Organization

There should be increased punishment of terrorist organization membership to powerful deterrent. In this case, the punishment for the convicted accuse is imprisonment for 10 years or fine or both, or 6 months summary conviction and fine but not exceed to the limit of the statute.

Moreover, there is also need to amend and differentiate between private and public meetings in sub-section 3(b) of section 11F. In this section include that for the cause of the proscribed organization meeting between two or more person privately. Likewise, it is best defense for accused to prove that the private meeting is not supporting proscribed organization.

There should be also added other defense of proscribed organization membership, that if accused ceased his membership to the organization which declared organization of terrorist then it will be right defense of accused. Additionally, there should also specify defense of the accused, if he isn't the member of that organization or hasn't participated in the work of that group. In order to this Act the proscribed organization's name should be mentioned, I First Schedule because still in this Act first Schedule isn't mentioned any name of proscribed organizations right now.

Moreover, proscribed organizations list would be published in the Pakistan Gazette in order to inform the people and save them from committing offence of terrorism under this Act. The list of the proscribed organization has increased clarity and knowledge for the general public. This will ensure for that individual who are not taking right of defense and not knowing that organization is proscribed.

To arrest an individual without a warrant should not bellowed SHO, who is wear clothing item, or display or carries an article, in such way to support proscribed organization. Moreover, for the criminal to present in court there must be limit of time and punishment for this offence in this Act should be also appropriated.

Recommendations Harmonize

This section harmonizes with constitution provision and the level of enforcing restrictions under section 11D and 11EE the word suspicion should be changed with reasonableness.

The word restrictions should be replaced with particular targeted restrictions for the purpose to reduce activity of the terrorists. For the Constitutional Rights the restriction should be more resalable to protect the affected.

There need a transparent method to be started for preventative individuals confinement in the Fourth Schedule list. The basis of the detention decision should be current information and his participation in activities of terrorist and detention wasn't made on that information and name included in the Fourth Schedule.

It is suggested, that sectarian word be deleted from this Act and replaced with word motivation of religion. This word isn't only newly presents two sects of on faith and does violence under this Act, but also violence has done by the member of the different sects faith. Broadly speaking, the language used in this Act is maintained and advancing the interest of the specific group is prejudice. Here only distinction of sectarian expressions between Sunni and Shia sects, this expression interreligious behavior.

According to Section 2(v) hatred of sectarian means, dislike against group of person i.e. religion, religious persuasion, religious belief or religious sect. Similar term also express in section 2(u) but the only difference is sectarian hatred has defined in the Act that hostility not only parent sect but also different religion. However, the word sectarian hatred defined in this Act more extensively the term sectarianism. By merging term, religious hatred with sectarian hatred has created a wide range of dispute within the definition. To solve this dispute wording of this Act is needed to replace with the wide range individual. However, the member of the judiciary may use this word in precise but in this Act uses an extensive variation of people than lawfully drill i.e. officials of law enforcement. The term sectarian hatred is minimized and detracts the transparency of this Act.

Additionally, for more clarity of definition, it is suggested that the sectarian hatred term be replaced by religious hatred. To the adding of new word covers violence of religion, but also it gives clarity to complex element. However, section 2(v) remains same with definition clause of ATA.

It is suggested that restraint hatred speech and incitement in this Act be substituted with broader as described in Cr.P.C. and PPC. This is earlier attention on sectarianism in Karachi in 1990s. But present time incitement is more complicated and it has multifaceted nature, terrorism, and it is needed for this Act to address these complexities.

Recommendations Terrorism Trials

There should be suitable worded and realistic approach use for concluding terrorism trial. The amendment includes minimum time line 3 months. If the case isn't concluded in given time period, then section 19(7) rule will be followed by the direction of High Court Judge to conclude the case in given time.

There should be a proper method in this Act that handling day-to-day terrorism case by the prosecutor. For speedy trial, this is necessary that Government issue notification with instruction to the Prosecutor and appear to ATCs. Additionally, terrorism trial will be a primary focus in the presence of other work of the Prosecutor. If Prosecutor fails to fulfill said notification duties, then he could be transferred or this case is hand over to other prosecutor.

The Government should initial conduct workshops for prosecutor and providing finalities at country level. This will increase insight and capacity in terrorism cases. This section is about the appointment of state lawyer (prosecutor) for the accused. However, there should need strict principal for starting the trail and strict attendance before Judge. For the adjournment of the trial pays minimum attention, if it is accused or prosecutor side.

Recommendations Internal System for High profile cases

There should be the internal system for high profile cases of terrorism. There should be ruled for the status of accused, i.e. designation, identity for rendering service associated with Pakistan and sort of crime. There should be instituted a committee which consists of one representative of the Government, one ATC Judge and one High Court Judge. The committee should decide that the case is started on immediate bases for the ends of justice.

Committee views the case of priority base under section 15 of ATA 1997. There should be kept accusing in undisclosed place where public and media attention is less because to protect from violent behavior of public in court areas. This will raise the spirit of this act and give speedy justice in high profile cases of the terrorism. The committee should be agreed with an ATC judge in backlog the cases and there should be a method in which trial moves forward cases on daily bases.

Recommendations Adequate Case Management and related mechanisms

There should be pre-trial procedure in ATCs before initiating the terrorism trial. Because this kind of hearing means that all parties to the case before judge discuss the crime that it falls within ambit of terrorism or not. The motive behind the introduction of this method has first examined the cases and then send for trial. It means ordinary criminal cases will not be considered in ATCs under section 6 of the ATA 1997.

Therefore, a system of process should be created that reduce the piles of cases and certify potential of ATC judges. This mechanism may be adopted that ATCs judge can transfer the case under section 23 of this Act or hear the case under section 23 of the ATA 1997. There should be a pre-trial hearing system to start the case. But the majority of cases pre-trial hearing has taken place after framing the charge against accused. It is suggested, that submission of Challan by Public Prosecutor the ATCs judge order hearing of pre-trial. The pre-trial restraint the judges to fulfill their duty not consider it burdensome. The judges should hear the cases and disposed them that these cases are not coming within the jurisdiction of terrorism. By adopting this procedure, reduce the burden of cases, which are not, come in terrorism ambit.

There should appoint more judges in order to conduct terrorism cases on the bases of fast track. This appointment of the judges wills less the responsibilities of present judges and extra work will maintain by other judges. The government should increase the retirement of judges because they have experienced and know the procedure and status of the cases. The transfer of judges to other court is unrealistic because it will not reduce terrorism cases but it is useless effort.

Recommendations Protection of the witness

There should be needed to take various steps to give protection to witnesses in cases of terrorism. For the protection of witnesses, some measures have taken under section 21 and some of measures have taken by statutory rule in this Act section 35. ATCs may take more procedure about protection of witnesses by the Chief Justice of High Court.

This 1997 Act, section 21 should be operationally that the judges allow holding the identity of the witness from accused and giving the protection order of the witnesses. In

investigation stage the prevention order of the witness identity reveal until the investigation is complete in Cr.P.C section 173. Witness identity wont be opened in statement or document in the time of investigation.

There should be procedure requirement order for the protection of witnesses at trial stage. By this order court protect identity of the witness appeared in proceeding or document in trial cases of terrorism. The documents are included that are given to accused under Sec. 241A and 265-C of Cr.P.C. and order sheet and judgment. Once ATCs passes the order protection, identity then further steps are being taken with the permission of the court. This step provides protection to witness and minimize the threat.

To adopt soft measure has aimed providing testifying of witness is simple and conducive. It is suggested for additional witness also provides protection during the trial of ATCs because it will increase witness contribution in trial of terrorism. This suggestion also imposes bar on to accused contacting with a witness. Additionally, if contact with accused takes place after prohibition order of the court then section 503 PPC intimidations raise on accused.

Police enhance protection for the witness. The police provide close protection and patrolling of witness home. The witness received call should be monitored. The witness should minimize his contact. In serious case, the place of witness has changed from the time being. This temporary relocation provides protection of the police.

3. Conclusion

To sum up, definition of terrorism in this Act is without adequate protection against the abuse and misuse of terrorism law. This law is also inadequate to achieve the purpose, i.e. to punish and counter the terrorism. Last decade in Pakistan, there is a loophole in present law to combat and punish the terrorist. However, this loophole is also due to political will of successive government that is not achieving terrorism law's goal. Due to this reason, anti-terrorism law was selectively used not equally based use.

There are also government soft policies towards terrorists that cannot reduce terrorist attacks. There is evidence of break of D.I Khan Jail and terrorist attack in Baluchistan. These terrorists are convicted in ATA1997 but instead of this former PPP government's imposed ban on death punishment, which is violating terrorism law but also enhanced the terrorist's morale. Some of terrorist's organizations are confident that they will release their fellow militants from jail.

There is a need to change Pakistan Anti-Terrorism Laws. This changing should be taking place from the start definition section6. To study of Section 6 ATA 1997, it is clear that in this section consist of legislative defect that is spread unwarranted level. But there are some recommendation discussed in this thesis work that in Pakistan this Act could not cover criminal law, because the presence of terrorism law cover all areas which aren't present in ordinary criminal law. According to Hasard definition, "that terrorism is due to bad law, along with bad politics, to clean people from definition, so they are direct criminals." Terrorism is not an ordinary criminal act but it is particular form of crime.

There are also a large number of differences in present ATA 1997 court management and power, so it is easy to change such area. It is mentioned above that there are a large number of discrepancies present in the work of ATCs. In the interpretation of law by judges that all party persons are present and take speedy proceeding. This is correct in this point that several number of problems faced to get their goal, but they do not compromise with judgment. The judges must give their judgment impartial and due diligence. The rush justice means to skip important point, justice rush is crush the justice. It is right that both prosecutor and defense lawyers are avoiding every day hearing. Additionally, prosecutor also faced a lot of hurdles to forward the witness but in most cases the witness is unwilling to give evidence. If above mentioned recommendations are accepted then it justice will go on right way.

There are many organizations and individual that is associated with terrorists. However, in this ATA 1997 there is a lacuna about criteria to declare an organization as proscribe. There are also no evidentiary criteria to declare an organization proscribe. To shield the right of individual and organization, there should be specific criteria to declare proscribing an organization or individual. There should be given right of review to proscribe organized by review committee. Moreover, committee role should be specified in this Act. When Federal Government, i.e. review committee feels that an organization is reforming in a given time, so there must be a provision to assess the applications. There is also a vacuum for proscribe organization to appeal right for purpose to run its welfare social activities. Because some organizations are not single entity, they also carry social activity. If the right of appeal should be given under section 11-E ATA1997 to that organization than they can carry on social welfare activities. Again, in this act there is a loophole to differentiate between meetings of public or private that support proscribes organizations. For clarification, this is needed to differentiate public and private meeting. So this differentiation gives right of defense to individual that he is not supported-proscribed organization.

The restriction imposed on proscribe organization is incredible and extensive because constitution provides right to move freely. Therefore, restriction imposed on the individual must be reasonable. The government has given special powers to detain and arrest persons that are in the Fourth Schedule. The purpose behind arresting that person too stops from terrorist activities and supporting proscribed organizations. It is necessary that detention of individuals based on participation in terrorist activities. The law enforcement authority must show that such person presently required in activity of terrorist and then detain the individual.

Money is foremost and first step to carry on terrorist activities. The different way used in Pakistan to collect money for terrorist's i.e. religious nature charities or transfer of funds collects money through extortion, money laundering, etc. Therefore, it is necessary to counter terrorism and dismantle the financial networks of the terrorists. So fully control the financing of terrorists in Pakistan it need completely implement action plan, i.e. adequately demonstrates finance of terrorism, to ensure Financial Intelligence Unit (FIU) that money is reasonable used and an adequate method to confiscate, freeze funds of terrorists, etc. However, in the presence of legal system still the record of combating money laundering is not satisfactory. Because there is the flaw of investigation system to ask from the powerful

agencies they're funding. However, there are not effective prosecutions in this Act. Presently, the provisions of CFT are not providing unambiguous and coherent structure to freeze and seize the assets of terrorist organizations or individual terrorists.

The rising violence of sectarian in the country, specially in Karachi the Anti-Terrorism Act 1997 was enforced to control sectarian conflict between Shia and Sunni sects. Such type of terrorism becomes the most dangerous and serious threat to State peace and unity. It must differentiate between religion, violence and religiously motivated violence. There is no inter-religious definition in this Act, section 2(u) and section 6. The absence of interreligious word was not cooped the sectarian violence. Presently increasing terrorist violence and to curb such violence, it is needed to include all kinds of religious motivated acts not only sectarian.

Regardless, in the presence many provisions of ATA about the powers of ATCs to conduct trial of terrorism but still uncertainty present in some sections. Due to these flaws, the power of ATCs judges also affected. Under section 19(7) of ATA, terrorism trial after its commencement must be disposed within 7 days. However, it does not happening because the defense lawyer always trying for adjournment. Another reason, which lengthens the trial that the majority of witnesses, are silent to give evidence due to the threat of the accused. It should be necessary that the wording of the section 19(7) of Anti-Terrorist Act 1997 is more practical approach to conclude trial of the terrorism. The Government should conduct workshops about facilitation to the prosecutors. The Judges interpret law, according to necessity. The judges are also facing a lot of difficulties to get their goals. Justice must not be fast track, but it served due diligence.

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